

Style for IRRN Contributors

Units of measure and styles vary from country to country. To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style guidelines:

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).

- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).

- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.

- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.

- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.

- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.

- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.

- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.

- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

- Type all contributions double-spaced. ¶

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

An attempt to improve local rice varieties through hybridization

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In an attempt to improve yield, disease resistance, and quality, the local varieties Nizershail and Tepi Boro were crossed with some IRRI strains. The segregating

generations were handled by a combination of pedigree and mass-selection breeding methods. Selection criteria were plant type and yielding ability. Seven F₆ lines are promising with respect to biochemical properties, disease reaction, plant type, and yield: AU16-1, AU21-6, AU16-19-20, AU16-21, AU41-15-18, AU19-3, and AU54-52 (see table). Two F₅ lines, 70.11 and 70.58, also look promising. ¶

Performance of new lines with respect to yield, biochemical constituents, and disease reaction, compared with that of their local parents. Bangladesh Agricultural University.

Line or variety ^a	Parents	Season to which the line was adapted	Yield (t/ha)	Biochemical constituents (%)		Disease reaction ^b		
				Protein	Amylose	Bacterial leaf streak	Bacterial leaf blight	Stem rot
AU21-6	Nizershail/IR532E-420	Aus	5.07	11.8	31	R	MR	R
AU16-1	Nizershail/IR578-175-2-2	Aus	5.35	9.5	28	R	R	MR
AU16-19-20	"	Aman	5.02	6.5	29	-	-	-
AU16-21	"	Aman	5.62	7.8	30	-	-	-
AU41-15-18	Nizershail/IR6-43-48	Aman	4.83	9.1	31	MR	-	-
AU19-3	Nizershail/IR532E-420	Aman	4.81	9.8	27	-	-	-
AU54-52	"	Aman	4.95	9.6	25	MR	-	-
AU70-11	Tepi Boro/IR140-136	Boro	4.95	-	30	MR	MR	R
AU70-58	"	Boro	5.26	-	30	MR	R	R
Nizershail	-	Aman	4.12	7.5	29	-	R	R
Tepi Boro	-	Boro	3.54	10.4	24	MR	R	MR

^aAU = Agricultural University. ^bR = moderately resistant; R = resistant.

IRRI's genetic resources program

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Since 1971 IRRI has collaborated with 12 national agricultural research centers in the field collection of indigenous rice germ plasm. Other workers who have cooperated in the canvassing of rice gene pools in remote areas include university faculty, missionary groups, international

service corps, extension workers, and botanists of other crops. The primary objectives of field collection are to save unimproved varieties that are endangered by the spread of modern varieties and to assemble the minor rices that have not yet been collected.

Since 1972 more than 18,000 seed samples have been collected from South and Southeast Asia; IRRI's staff helped collect more than 7,500 of them. About 4,850 of the samples are reputed to have one or more special characters, such as

resistance to or tolerance for pests, adverse soils, cool temperature, or drought.

In recent years, IRRI has initiated systematic seed exchange with China, India, and the USSR. Several rice research centers in India have provided IRRI with duplicate sets of their rice collections. More than 6,000 samples were thus acquired in 1976–77.

The IRRI germ plasm bank supplies thousands of seed samples to rice researchers every year. Distribution has increased markedly since IRRI expanded its Genetic Evaluation and Utilization Program in 1974 (see table).

To meet the expanded flow of seeds to and from IRRI, construction of a Rice Genetic Resources Laboratory began late in 1976. The new laboratory will expand storage and working areas and will

Progress of the IRRI Genetic Resources Program in field collection, preservation, and seed distribution of *Oryza sativa* cultivars. IRRI, 1970–77.

Year	Samples collected in Asia (no.)	Distinct accessions in germ plasm bank (no.)	Samples distributed (no.)	
			Inside IRRI	To national programs
1970	—	12,800	16,000	5,660
1971	907	14,712	10,600	2,300
1972	4,177	16,893	2,740	2,500
1973	5,004	24,162	8,275	9,777
1974	2,149	26,818	19,236	2,603
1975	5 06	30,332	22,155	4,043
1976	1,670	34,229	40,200	4,819
Mid-1977	463	36,851 ^a	26,303	3,628

^aAbout 6,278 recently received seed samples are yet to be registered; 4,646 duplicate accessions and 1,822 nonviable seed samples were removed from the collection from 1972 to 1977.

include a new facility for long-term seed storage. When completed in November 1977, it will house the Plant Breeding Department and the International Rice Testing Program. In December 1977 a

workshop sponsored jointly by the International Board for Plant Genetic Resources and IRRI will develop further plans for worldwide collaboration on the conservation of rice germ plasm.

Survey of environmental and biological problems related to rice growing in Asia

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Thirty-five rice breeders at 28 research centers in 10 Asian nations were asked to rank, in order of severity, the four most serious environmental and biological problems (drought, cold temperature, injurious soils, diseases and insects, etc.) that limit farmers' rice yields within the area served by each experiment station. At stations where more than one rice breeder was interviewed, the data were collected for the major subregion for which each breeder was responsible. The survey was in collaboration with Iowa State University, USA, and was partially funded by a Rockefeller Foundation grant.

Every breeder surveyed rated diseases and insects as one of his four major problems (see table). For all regions, pests received the highest mean severity rating — 3.2 on a scale where 4 = the most serious problem and 1 = the fourth most serious. Drought was the second most important environmental stress. Considered a major problem in 82% of the areas, drought also received the second highest mean severity rating. Its overall rating was 2.2 out of a possible 4.

Rice breeders' perceptions of the biological and environmental stresses that most seriously limit rice production on farmers' fields within the areas served by their research centers. Thirty-five rice breeders at 28 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 10 Asian nations, 1975.

Biological/environmental factors	Mean severity rating ^a		Rated as major constraint ^b (%)
	All stations	Stations where a problem	
Diseases and insects	3.2	3.2	100
Drought	2.2	2.7	82
Injurious soils	1.2	2.2	57
Excessive monsoon cloudiness	1.3	2.4	40
Floods	0.6	1.7	38
Cold temperature	0.7	2.5	29
Deep water	0.4	2.6	15
Hot temperature	0.1	1.3	9
Waterlogged soil	0.1	2.5	6
Others ^c	0.1	1.5	6

^aOn a scale of 1–4: 4 = most serious environmental or biological stress; 1 = fourth most serious. Calculated for all 35 areas and also for only those in which each factor was considered one of the region's four major problems.

^bPercent of 35 rice breeders that rated each stress as one of four most serious problems limiting rice production on farmers' fields within the regions served by the experiment stations.

^cTyphoons and weeds.

When calculated for only those stations where drought was considered a serious problem, its mean severity rating was 2.7. Injurious soils (salinity, alkalinity, zinc deficiency, etc.) were rated as a major constraint in 57% of the regions. The severity rating for injurious soils was 1.2 for all stations and 2.2 for the stations where they were considered serious.

Excessive monsoon cloudiness was a serious constraint in 40% of the regions, and floods were a major problem in 38%.

Cold temperature, rated as a problem in 29% of the areas, received a low overall severity rating of 0.7. But when calculated for only the stations where cold was a problem, its severity rating was high, 2.5. Deep water was defined as "water that reaches about 50 cm (too deep for semidwarf varieties to grow) during the monsoon season." Deep water received an overall severity rating of 0.4; but in the 15% of the regions where it was considered a problem, its severity rating was high, 2.6.